

Granting Accessible Tourism for Everyone – GATE

Report on the IT Applications of the Pilot Sites

Monitoring & Lessons Learned

Partners with Pilot IT Applications:

CAI Alpago | Commune de Santorso | Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, with independent L. | Salzburg Research, in partnership with SalzburgerLand

Research Partner:

Report edited by Guntram Geser, Salzburg Research

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1 Introduction and overview

1.1 The GATE Project

GATE, Granting Accessible Tourism for Everyone, is a cross-border cooperation of partners located in Austria and Italy aimed to promote barrier-free touristic offers for all in the Alpine and pre-Alpine regions. Development of inclusive tourism should enable improved accessibility of natural areas for people with disabilities, contributing also to the regional valorisation of the areas.

For these purposes the GATE project focuses on the use of information technologies that allow providing information about the accessibility of sites such as nature parks and hiking trails as well as engaging experiences when visiting the sites. As an important part of the project, partners developed IT applications to demonstrate these capabilities for four pilot areas and sites.

1.2 Overview of the pilot sites

The GATE website presents each of the four pilot sites on a dedicated webpage. The figure below shows the entry to these webpages, which briefly describe the sites and their IT application(s), and provide links and contact information.

This report now gives a detailed account of the development of the IT applications of the pilot sites. In brief, the applications are:

<p>Virtual Reality Geoparc Bletterbach Experience implemented at the GEOMuseum Redagno</p> <p>In addition, as showcase implementations of GATE IT tools, a multimedia guide and chatbot have been developed for the Bletterbach area¹</p>	<p>Parco Rossi INgame an interactive adventure chatbot for learning about the history, architecture and landscape of the park</p> <p>Villa Rossi 3D a tactile and talking model of the villa</p>	<p>Easy Hikes Information platform for 82 hikes (and other attractions) for families with small children in the Pongau region of Salzburg, 35 of the hikes possible with a stroller</p>	<p>Sentiero della Sensibilità A 24 km hiking trail adapted for visitors with disabilities (incl. dedicated panels), Web app multimedia guide and 14 stations with iBeacons that trigger cultural and landscape information</p>
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¹ See: GATE (2020). Report on the Accessibility Tools with Showcase Implementations. Edited by Guntram Geser, Salzburg Research, 27 November 2020.

1.3 Monitoring of the IT applications

This GATE report presents the results of the monitoring of the IT applications of the four pilot sites of the project, including lessons learned in the development of the applications.

As part of the project work plan a monitoring of the development had to be conducted. This has been carried out through:

- Presentations and discussion of the ongoing development at the pilot sites in project meetings;
- Reporting of each pilot partner based on a template on different aspects of the development, followed up by communication on relevant details to generate a comprehensive documentation;
- Visits to learn about the conditions at the sites were planned, but only the GEOPARC Bletterbach could be visited on the 25th of October 2019, accessing the other sites became impossible due to the COVID-19 restrictions.

The sections of Chapter 2 present the monitoring reports for the IT applications of the pilot sites. Each report first provides information about the background and a brief description of the IT application(s), followed by details of the development, testing, launch and promotion, user feedback/data, and plans for next steps. For special technologies such as augmented reality animations or virtual reality also details about the production, user environment and other aspects are included.

Chapter 3 summarises important lessons learned by the pilot partners in the realisation of the IT applications.

2 Monitoring reports

2.1 Virtual Reality Experience Bletterbach Gorge

2.1.1 Background and brief description

GATE partner: Fondazione Dolomiti UNESCO, with support by independent L.

Region/country: Aldein/Aldino, South Tyrol, Italy.

Pilot site: GEOPARC Bletterbach area and visitor centre in Aldino, GEOMuseum in Redagno

Website: www.bletterbach.info

Contact e-mail: Guenther.Ennemoser@independent.it

Brief description of the site:

The Bletterbach gorge and wider area is part of the UNESCO World Heritage of the Dolomites and presents itself as an open book in which it is possible to read over 40 million years of our planet's history. The area is particularly attractive for people with an interest in geology and nature, hikers, families and school classes.

Number of visitors: In the summer season the number of visitors of the GEOPARC Bletterbach can reach over 50.000.²

VR application and content:

The technical solution of the Virtual Reality Experience Bletterbach Gorge has been developed by the company Dimension (Trento) for the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, under the coordination of independent L. (Merano). The application is based on 360°VR video technology and is used with a VR headset. The virtual tour is available in three languages, Italian, German, English, with infographics. The narrative content is suitable for visitors of all ages. The story focuses on the gorge, for example, how geologists reconstructed its formation by analysing the rocks. The VR application is implemented at the GEOMuseum Redagno in a specially adapted barrier-free room. With the application, visitors of the Bletterbach area who cannot access the Bletterbach gorge due to mobility or other restrictions can still experience it in 3D. Actually, they can not only "fly" through the gorge but also perceive the whole area as the content includes sequences captured from above using a drone. However, the application is of interest to everyone, for example when access to the gorge and other areas is not possible due to weather conditions.

Additional applications:

In the project also showcase implementations of three GATE tools have been created for the GEOPARC Bletterbach area³:

- *Webapp Geoparc Guide:* Demonstrates the use of the accessible GATE Webapp for multimedia contents. The mobile guide explains the UNESCO World Heritage area and invites hikers on the

² UnserTirol24 (2018): GEOPARC Bletterbach stärkt Zusammenarbeit mit Wissenschaft (04.01.2018), <https://www.unsertirol24.com/2018/01/04/geoparc-bletterbach-staerkt-zusammenarbeit-mit-wissenschaft/>

³ See: GATE (2020). Report on the Accessibility Tools with Showcase Implementations. Edited by Guntram Geser, Salzburg Research, 27 November 2020.

Jochgrimm–Gurndinalm trail to experience the landscape and nature. On the trail at 8 points of interest equipped with QR-codes allow calling up special information.

- *Chatbot Bletterbach*: The “Bletterbot” interactively informs potential visitors about the GEOPARC Bletterbach area, opening hours of facilities, bus connections, etc. It is implemented on the Facebook page of the GEOPARC Bletterbach.
- *Bletterbach POIs*: Demonstrates the GATE IT Tool that allows organisations tag on an online map (e.g. Open Street Map) points of interest and provide information about their accessibility. The plugin can be easily integrated into websites based on WordPress.

Information about the shareable tools, such as content templates or program code, is being provided by the GATE partner independent L.

2.1.2 Development

Collaboration and production plan

The Bletterbach Gorge VR application was commissioned by the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO from the company Dimension (Trento), specialised in such products, and the scheduled implementation was coordinated by independent L. (Merano), who are experts in barrier-free physical and digital solutions.

The development team consisted of representatives of the production company, an expert in didactic narrative forms, curators of the GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitor Centre and Museum of Nature South Tyrol (Bolzano) regarding the scientific content, and the work coordinator independent L. The user interests have been taken account of in the development by convening workshops of the participants to define the concept and design of the application as well as testing a prototype with end-users.

The production plan for the Bletterbach Gorge VR foresaw work over four months from commissioning to installation of the final application. The realization of the VR experience cost 35.000,00 Euro (plus VAT) for the work by Dimension, and the additional effort of the other experts mentioned as well as the GEOMuseum operator where the VR application is installed.

The production plan included:

- The commissioning and project kick-off with partners,
- Interviews with stakeholders,
- Collection of scientific material and on-site inspection and photo shooting,
- Introduction of the content developers to the capabilities of the VR technology,
- Development of the storyboard and script,
- Video and sound recordings on-site,
- Post-production video and sound, script translation and narration by professional speakers,
- Testing with users and improvements,
- Installation of the VR experience station.

Due to the clean-up of the damages by the “Vaja” wind storm in spring 2019, the local inspection had to be postponed and the activity therefore started with a delay. Further delays were caused by the early onset of winter in autumn 2019, and the corona crisis in the first half of 2020, which meant that the planned schedule could not be met.

Narrative and VR content

The narrative content of the VR application has been developed in a collaboration of the expert in didactic narrative forms and the scientific experts of the Museum of Nature South Tyrol and curators

of the GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitor Centre. For the content a storyboard and script had to be developed, taking care that the content is suitable for visitors of all ages. For the narration the figure Maya was invented that accompanies the user on the VR excursion into the Bletterbach gorge and tells him/her how geologists reconstructed the formation of this impressive site by examining the rocks.

The digital 360°VR video recordings of the Bletterbach gorge and environment have been carried out with a high-resolution 3D camera (6K at 60FPS and 10K at 30FPS) mounted on a drone. In addition, high quality audio recordings were made in the gorge for the background noise.

The video recordings had to be edited and brought together with the narrative content for the VR experience in the different language versions, German, Italian and English, by a professional speaker. The recordings were edited into a long and a short version (12 and 5 minutes, respectively), adapted both visually and acoustically, and professionally set to music. Finally, in the three language versions subtitles for users with a hearing disability were added.

In addition, a short promotional teaser in the mentioned three languages and Italian sign language was produced to draw attention to the innovative IT application for the pilot area GEOPARC Bletterbach.

2.1.3 User testing

The user interests were first taken account of by convening workshops of representatives of the production company Dimension, the client the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, GEOPARC Bletterbach, GEOMuseum Radegno, Museum of Nature South Tyrol, and independent L, who are experts for barrier-free physical and digital solutions (e.g. the adaptation plan for removing architectural barriers at the GEOMuseum). An evaluation of the design and testing of the VR experience took place in a plenum with the involvement of an expert for digital accessibility.

Regarding the digital accessibility two improvements were requested and implemented which concerned the graphic design of the title and logo in the opening sequence and infographics displayed in the middle of the film to visualise certain information. In the former case, the originally intended trembling graphic effect for the fonts and the logos was removed, and in the latter the entire display format for showing geological layers was revised.

A working version of the VR application has been presented to interested test persons on the 24th and 25th of September 2019 at the EU project fair at Maretsch Castle in Bolzano, and on the 18th of December 2019 at the international conference “Assistive Technologies, Health and Autonomy” at the EURAC Research Centre in Bolzano.

This conference gave an overview of the most innovative applications of information and communication technologies in the rehabilitation and support of people with functional impairments in everyday life. The feedback of the test persons was consistently positive and encouraged us to proceed according to plan. As one testimonial:

“This is really cool, I can't get enough of it, such incredibly beautiful nature. If there is no one waiting to test the experience, I would like to watch the movie again”, said an elderly person (architect) who tested the Bletterbach Gorge VR at the EU project fair in Bolzano.

2.1.4 User environment and VR experience

The VR station has been installed in the GEOMuseum Redagno, in the barrier-free film room. A short video, currently in Italian and Italian sign language LIS, introduces the visitors to the Bletterbach Gorge VR and the use of the technology.

The VR viewer Oculus Go is an independent system with headphones integrated in the device. This is not only practical for the user, who can use the viewer independently, but also beneficial for the museum, as it does not need additional personnel supervising the new experience station.

In addition to the portable all-in-one VR headset, the VR experience station has been equipped with two stable viewer chairs with barrier-free armrests to make it easier for senior citizens and visitors with disabilities to sit down and get up.

The VR headset can be operated without assistance. The visitor puts on the headset, selects the preferred language, and the digital tour of the Bletterbach Gorge VR starts automatically. The virtual visitor experience lasts about 12 minutes. With the VR application museum visitors can not only “fly” through the gorge but also perceive the whole area as the content includes film sequences captured from above with a drone.

In case of discomfort, the user can remove the headset at any time. For particularly sensitive users, supervision by an accompanying person is advisable. Most of the people who tested the technology were enthusiastic and watched the virtual tour of the Bletterbach gorge until the end. Only few users have difficulties getting used to the digital 3D format feeling a discomfort in the first seconds.

When not in use, the headset is returned to the charging station, and can then be used again at any time. If there is a large number of visitors, the museum can decide to show the shorter version of about 5 minutes.

Because of the current protective measures due to the COVID-19 crisis, disposable cardboard viewers for smartphones (Google Card DIY mobile phone VR 3D glasses) have been purchased, so that visitors can watch the VR without exposing their health to any risk.

2.1.5 Launch and promotion

The VR station has been installed on the 13th of October 2020 at the GEOMuseum Redagno in the barrier-free film room. To attract visitors, a teaser with versions in English, German, Italian and Italian sign language LIS has been produced. The teaser is published on YouTube and is promoted on the GATE project and Bletterbach Geoparc websites.

Furthermore, the Bletterbach IT applications are networked with each other, so that the Bletterbach Gorge VR is also promoted in the Webapp Geoparc Guide and the Bletterbot (Chatbot Bletterbach) to generate additional visitors for the GEOMuseum.

2.1.6 User feedback and data

User feedback has been collected in the preparation and testing of the VR application as described above. The GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitors Centre will fill in an evaluation form describing how the application has been integrated in the daily operation of the GEOMuseum in Redagno. Data on the access to and experience of the VR station in the museum will be collected through the admission tickets and a feedback question included in the visitor questionnaire, which the GEOMuseum uses for quality assurance.

After the forthcoming new construction of the GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitor Centre, a VR station is also planned there to make the developed technology available to as many users as possible. In the visitor centre data on the usage of the application will also be collected through the admission tickets and a feedback question on the VR experience in the visitor questionnaire.

Because of the Corona crisis, the operator of the GEOPARC Bletterbach visitor facilities was hesitant to open them this year. After long deliberations with the local government, the operator decided to open the Bletterbach Geoparc, but with a much reduced number of staff. Therefore, it was not possible this year to provide services that were not absolutely necessary for the maintenance of operations.

This also included the visitor survey, which is interrupted for the first time in about 10 years, because the handling of the questionnaires is time consuming, if not impossible at all, due to the necessary COVID-19 safety measures.

2.1.7 Plans for next steps

The development of the Bletterbach Gorge Virtual Reality enables an inclusive visitor experience in the GEOMuseum Redagno for all, with and without disabilities. Following the planned new construction of the GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitor Centre, a VR station with the same equipment is planned also there, with an introductory video for waiting visitors.

In the future, it could also be considered to provide a third experience station in the much-visited Museum of Nature South Tyrol, in the exhibition area Geology, to arouse interest in the Bletterbach gorge and the World Heritage Dolomites at a satellite point.

The VR application could in the future be the starting point for the development of an experimental version for people with visual impairments, i.e. an acoustic 3D surround nature experience.

2.2 Parco Rossi – INgame and Villa Rossi 3D

2.2.1 Background and brief description

GATE partner: Comune di Santorso

Region/country: Province of Vicenza, Italy

Pilot site: Parco Rossi in Santorso

Website: www.parcorossi.it

Contact e-mail: antonio.demartin@comune.santorso.vi.it

Brief description of the site:

Parco Rossi is a romantic garden of high landscape value. It is the cornerstone of a complex system located on the slopes of Mount Summano, which includes upstream the Villa Rossi and the park and downstream the model farm. Founded by Alessandro Rossi between 1865 and 1884, the Parco Rossi is among the outstanding examples of nineteenth century landscape parks of northern Italy. Here visitors can experience all the typical elements of such a park, including a lake, an impressive array of exotic and native plants, sinuous paths, rustic architecture, and other appealing elements.

Number of visitors: Summer season, around 3.000 visitors⁴

Applications and content:

Parco Rossi is an inclusive heritage communication project with the aim to make the history, architecture and landscape of the park accessible to all visitors based on the principles of Design for All. A barrier-free visitor system and a multimedia guide with 19 stories in different languages (English, Italian and Italian sign language), triggered by iBeacons, already supported visitors to discover the park. In the framework of the GATE project new applications have been implemented: INgame is a reality game with a chatbot, an “intelligent” interactive chat system (ingame.parcorossi.it). Visitors do not have to download and install the game, but use a Web app with their smartphone or tablet. With the chatbot they can take three routes in the park and have a variety of options regarding language (Italian, Italian Sign Language, English, German) as well as interaction mode (e.g. visual with texts and images or audio-guide). The multimodal approach allows meeting the access needs of visitors with sight or hearing impairments and an engaging park experience for all. Furthermore, a panel with a 3D tactile and talking relief of the Villa Rossi has been created. The panel allows visitors with a visual impairment (and others) to learn about the Villa Rossi, its architecture and the history of the people who lived here.

2.2.2 Development of INgame

Multi-disciplinary development team

For the development of INgame a multi-disciplinary team with synergies between the members’ different expertise was necessary. The areas of development and leading team members were:

- *The narrative dimension:* Dramaturgy structure, storyboard, game design, animations and historical re-enactments, and production secretariat: La Piccionaia - Centro di Produzione Teatrale.

⁴ Parco Rossi (2016): Un’estate con più di 3.000 visitatori (4 ottobre 2016), <http://www.parcorossi.it/unestate-piu-3-000-visitatori/>

- *The digital dimension:* Software and Web development, following good practices of code versioning, automated testing, compliance with PHP standards (PHP-FIG / PSR) and privacy first design; video and augmented reality production, user-friendly chat interface and experience design: DonQ.

More specifically, the INgame technology stack is mainly based on Open Source technologies including the Operating system (Ubuntu Linux), programming language (PHP 7.x), database (MySQL), chatbot development framework (Laravel and Botman), and Augmented Reality (Arjs) framework.

- *The Design for All dimension:* Elements necessary for the customization of the game for users with different disabilities, ensuring that texts and images for the chat interface are readable and comprehensible, translations from Italian to Italian sign language (LIS), English and German, tests with users, and overall accessibility management: Parco Rossi team with the accessibility expert Diana De Tomaso.

The INgame development process followed an “agile” methodology, including a 14 days sprint of software programming, execution and testing; weekly short meetings of the development team for development status reporting; monthly meetings for project management and alignment of all groups working on the application; and one test with expert users and two tests with end-users.

2.2.3 Game customization

INgame is a reality game with an interactive “intelligent” chat system for use on smartphones or tablets. With a Progressive WebApp it is not necessary to download the application on the device. The game allows the user to discover the secrets of the park thanks to the tales, animated graphics, historical re-enactments and quizzes. The game dynamics are structured on missions to be carried out and explorers’ site search – the visitor is the protagonist of a game of exploration. The player is guided on the selected game path by the little dragon ARAC as virtual assistant.

The most important aspect of INgame regarding inclusiveness is the possibility to personalise the game. The user can choose:

- One of the four languages available: Italian, Italian sign language, German and English;
- The preferred media mode: audio mode, designed for visually impaired people; text - images designed for people with a hearing impairment, or all modes for people without any particular difficulties;
- One of the three playing fields, which are the yellow, green and blue paths in the park, each with a different level of physical accessibility.

2.2.4 Animations and re-enactments

Augmented Reality elements

As Augmented Reality (AR) elements of INgame videos of animated graphics and historical re-enactments have been produced:

- Videos for two different animated graphics of ARAC, the little dragon that interacts with the INgame users and helps them explore the park;
- Three historical re-enactment videos:
 - Two videos (30 seconds each) in which at the begin Alessandro Rossi introduces the visitor to INgame and at the end thanks them for playing the game;
 - One video (90 seconds) set around 1870, with costumed actors, in which Alessandro Rossi introduces the visitor to his house, where a dance party is taking place.

In INgame these elements serve the following purposes: The animated graphics of ARAC promote the player's involvement, reinforcing the playful and friendly nature of the park. The re-enactment videos enable the appearance of historical persons and environments with corresponding emotional effects.

Animated graphics

The animation of the little dragon ARAC can serve as an example of what needs to be considered when incorporating Augmented Reality (AR) features in a Web app. AR means that in real-world scenes app users see through the camera of the smartphone or tablet inserted artificial elements such as historical persons or objects.

In close cooperation with the technical IT team, it was evaluated that the best format for integrating animated graphics in the Web app is GIF images. This is mainly due to the data volume, which for a Web app needs to be as low as possible, so that it can be used with most mobile devices, including not the latest generation regarding the operating system and other aspects.

For the animated graphics of ARAC it was decided to give it in the videos a cartoonish look in the movements. In the first video ARAC emerges from a fantastic portal, and then gets on the ground and waves at the player. In the second video the portal appears in the center of the image and then moves to the right revealing ARAC, who leaps out and gets himself in the scene, always beckoning to the player.

Furthermore, to keep the animation light, a GIF image was created for use in a loop. This solution allows the character to stay in the scene, not static but seemingly alive. The transparent background allows anchoring the animation to the marker (geotag) and integrate it with the background captured by the camera of the smartphone or tablet.

Features for impaired users

The animated graphics and historical re-enactments come with special features for users with disabilities:

- The historical re-enactment videos are available in Italian, Italian sign language (LIS) and English, with subtitles, for people with a hearing impairment;
- All videos have a dramaturgy and a voice over that supports the use of the game by blind people;
- The graphic animations of ARAC are accompanied by recorded speech and subtitles which makes them suitable for users with sight and hearing impairments;
- The video set in the Villa Rossi allows users with reduced mobility to get to know parts of the interior of the villa, which at present is not accessible from the park in a wheelchair.

The videos provide an emotional immersion in the atmosphere of Alessandro Rossi's age that supports the involvement also of people with cognitive disabilities.

2.2.5 User testing

INgame has been developed as an inclusive IT application with the aim to allow visitors with disabilities (and others) an immersive experience of the park in an autonomous, comfortable and safe way. The principles of Design for All and user-centered design have been applied to ensure participation of users in the development – as consultants in the design phase (1 test with expert users) and as on-site testers in the implementation phase (2 tests with target users). Young and elderly people, with a sight or hearing disability, and wheelchair users have been involved.

The consultants and testers have made important contributions to the development of INgame. They greatly appreciated the innovativeness of the project and their feedback has always been very positive and encouraging. Several improvements of the functionality and content could be made thanks to their suggestions. In the last testing phase, several days of inspections of INgame allowed us to fine-tune the application, especially the game workflow editing and the GPS positioning.

2.2.6 The Villa Rossi 3D model

Within the GATE project, also a panel with a 3D tactile and talking relief of the Villa Rossi has been created. The panel allows visitors with a visual impairment (and others) to learn about the Villa Rossi, its architecture and the history of the people who lived here.

The Villa Rossi 3D tactile and talking model – Parco Rossi, Commune di Santorso.

Basically the system consists of three elements:

- A tactile surface: designed and printed with contrasting colours for good readability and embossed text in Braille;
- 3D printed elements: representing the Villa's façade and details;
- A series of Capacitive sensors are triggered when touching model elements with the tips of the finger and activate audio descriptions and stories.

Features for accessibility

The panel has been designed with a focus on Design for All. The relief of the model, graphical elements and contrasts are tailored for visually impaired visitors, and the panel and its elements are also very well accessible for wheelchair users and children.

The relief model and touch sensors follow a logical and tidy path, starting from a general exploration of the villa and then moving deeper to the details. The Capacitive touch sensors are embedded inside the panel and respond effectively to light touch of sensitive relief/model elements. The audio tracks, currently in Italian and English, are paired by Braille signs to support a full tactile exploration.

Implementation and testing

The Parco Rossi team collaborated with organisations with the required special expertise:

- Tooteko Srls (Venezia): designed the panel and managed the printing of the 3D tactile elements based on additive stereolithography techniques;
- Tactile Vision Onlus (Turin): supported the evaluation and selection of the graphics of the panel and the printing of the braille embossed signs;
- La Piccionaia - Centro di Produzione Teatrale (Padova): recorded the audio tracks with speakers in Italian and English.

Tooteko experts in solutions for visually impaired people carried out a functional testing of the tactile elements and audio content. Finally the panel was tested by end-users involving visually impaired persons and others, including children.

2.2.7 Launch, user feedback and data

INgame and the Villa Rossi 3D model have been launched on the 27th of September 2020 in a public event in the Parco Rossi. Over 100 people attended the event to learn about the brand new applications.

As INgame is a Web application the access and usage can be monitored with Google Analytics. The analysis is based on aggregated anonymous data and various filters for dates, event types, interactions, etc. can be applied. Before and during the launch event and into October 2020 INgame has been used by 304 people. In September 2020, 211 users started INgame, 3.433 interactions took place (e.g. stations started, stations skipped, spools started, spools finished), and 56 users completed the whole game.

In the video interviews during the launch event to collect feedback on the new applications and experience of the park all interviewees reported the highest level of fun and satisfaction (collected with the use of emoticons). Some examples of feedback statements by children are:

- *“The thing I liked most about Ingame was playing Memory”* (with details of the Parco Rossi) – Riccardo, 8 years old.
- *“The thing that I liked the most was looking for the Arac dragon”* (iconic figure of the park in the augmented reality of INgame) – Enrico, 12 years old.
- *“The thing I liked the most was ‘entering the dance hall’ of the Villa”* (thanks to the historical film inserted in INgame) – Gabriele, 12 years old.

It is also worth noting that in September 2020, when the launch event was promoted, spontaneous comments of visitors of the Parco Rossi website increased significantly. The comments were at the maximum level of satisfaction (5/5 points), except of one case (4/5 points) related to the villa not a visit of the park.

2.2.8 Plans for next steps

For the next year a promotion and communication campaign is planned that will particularly feature the new applications for inclusive access to the Parco Rossi.

A review of the website is intended to optimise the presentation of the many physical and digital ways Parco Rossi provides to experience the park and learn about its history, architecture and landscape.

came to the office while only 200 guests from other countries (-66%). Thus during the Corona crisis there were significantly more Italian day tourists in the area to enjoy the natural environment while of course much less from other countries.

Web app and information panels:

The Web App Sentiero della Sensibilità provides a guide for the hiking trail of 24 km, including multimedia information about the cultural landscape of the Alpage. There are several access points to the trail. At the three main points, panels give initial orientation and information in Italian, German and English, including in Braille. A system of panels developed specifically for the trail informs about which stretches are suitable in case of a disability (mobility, sight), directions and distances, and resting places.

For a number of special places along the trail the Web App provides rich multimedia contents. It can also be used as an audio-guide in Italian, English and German. The Web App is available for Android- and iOS-based devices. Via Bluetooth the app can communicate with 12 iBeacons that are placed along the route and alert users about available special content.

In addition to the information about the cultural landscape, a musical path has been created that features the symphony par excellence dedicated to the mountains: The Alpine Symphony of Richard Strauss, composed between 1911 and 1915. The user can listen to short parts of the symphony that evoke landscapes, sounds and emotions that can be experienced in the mountains.

2.3.2 Development

Collaboration

The Sentiero della Sensibilità goes through the areas of three municipalities and seven Regole, which are collective properties belonging to local families. This required agreements and cooperation with and among these public and private entities in order to share the definition of the trail and to decide on the most suitable access points. They supported making the trail barrier-free as well as the installation of iBeacons. Moreover, the municipalities will support also in future the trail maintenance for the stretches in their areas of competence.

A close collaboration of CAI Alpage was also necessary with the Web App supplier to define all details of the Web App ensuring its easy use and attractiveness. The development of the Alpage pilot benefited also from the expertise of project partners, for example, exchanges with the Municipality of Santorso (Parco Rossi) regarding the use of Braille in information panels, and with independent L. on the concept of the Web App for users with disabilities.

Realisation

Web App technology was selected for the multimedia guide because of its high versatility in terms of both usability and flexibility regarding contents, e.g. the option to include additional content in future updates. The solution should also not take up too much data space of the mobile device of the user.

The Web App structure was developed starting from the existing Sentieri Parlanti (“talking trails”) of CAI Veneto, considering that the Veneto Region may intend bringing together different regional apps in a common platform. The goal for the multimedia guide was that it should be as easy as possible to use. The professionalism and high-quality orientation of the Web App supplier was a very important factor for the success of the project, including the adaptation of app standards to specific needs as in our case.

CAI Alpage volunteers helped with the production of the different content elements. The implementation of the contents was carried out with support by an expert in media for users with disabilities. Such users were of course involved in the development and testing of the Web App for the hiking trail.

2.3.3 User testing and feedback

In the development of the hiking trail and Web App, CAI Alpage volunteers met with people with disabilities to present the project and collect information about needs and suggestions regarding the implementation. Important aspects to consider in the Web App implementation, for example, included no software or contents to be downloaded directly in the personal mobile device, easy access to contents, easy recognition of “talking points” (available audio information on POIs), and best colours to use.

GATE partner independent L. tested the developed app regarding the success criteria of the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG 2.1)⁵ and usability, and the suggested improvements were implemented. The testing in the field was carried out along the first four kilometers of the Sentiero della Sensibilità, starting from the locality “Carota”, one of the three access points to the trail, on to the locality “I Girli”. This is a fairly flat stretch of the path that oscillates between 980 and 1050 meters above sea level, with short ascents and descents, and both paved and unpaved sections. This allowed testing the accessibility of the path regarding the physical conditions as well as the use of the Web App.

On the testing day the application was downloaded by 10 participants three of which with impairments, two visually impaired and one wheelchair user. The group included also a family with a small child in a stroller. The app was downloaded on smartphones using the QR-code on the information panel at the trail access point Carota. The duration of the app testing was about three hours and included the working of the Internet connection, GPS location, interactivity of the iBeacons, and access to the Web contents. All contents were used, i.e. texts and images, audio supports as well as the music. The participants used the smartphone holding it in their hands and without headphones.

⁵ W3C (2018): Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1. W3C Recommendation, 5 June 2018, <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>

Feedback by all users was collected with questions during the hike and interviews with the participants with disabilities at the endpoint. Responses were collected on the overall accessibility of the trail according to one's disability, the degree of satisfaction with the Web App, and the experience of the visit compared to previous ones of mountainous environments.

The recorded feedback on the Web App was analysed to identify possible further improvements. In general, the feedback concerning the accessibility and contents of the Web App was very positive. Very much appreciated was the musical part that expresses the enjoyment of the mountains. Regarding the graphical elements of the Web App some changes were recommended, for example, increasing the size of icons to make them easier to use for people with disabilities. The improvements will be implemented before the end of the GATE project. Some of the recorded feedback will be used also in a GATE training webinar on barrier-free access to mountain areas.

Selected feedback by participants with a disability:

"I must be honest, the Sentiero della Sensibilità is a path that fits well for a person in a wheelchair. I was able to do it all independently as far as I am here now (Location i Girli) and this is done absolutely in peace because it is a wide road, the slopes are never so demanding, the dirt road is still compact, so easily accessible even in a wheelchair. The Web App is well functioning." – Wheelchair user.

"The Path of Sensitivity seemed to me to be practicable almost all by myself, I tried to keep the edge always and almost always was possible except when there were some openings that I think are always intercept." – Partially visually impaired person.

"I really liked the idea of having both an explanation of the place, the origin of the term, and a musical track that in my opinion is complete. Surely there could be activities that make it even more complete, just for children something more interactive or manual could be an idea." – Partially visually impaired person.

2.3.4 Launch and promotion

The first version of the Sentiero della Sensibilità app has been made available on the 31th of October 2020 in the App stores for Android and iOS devices so that interested people can download it. Due to the restrictions imposed by the anti-Covid regulations, this was a "soft launch" with only limited promotion, mainly making selected people aware that the application is available to try and give feedback. Thus, so far, the CAI Alpago development team, disabled people involved in the testing, some members of CAI Alpago and GATE partners have been involved.

2.3.5 Plans for next steps

Before the end of the GATE project, information materials will be produced for distribution in 2021 at the places of greatest tourist influx and information points in the Alpago area. Thereby visitors will be made aware of the barrier-free hiking trail and that they can access the Web App via a QR-code before starting their hike. The broad outreach and promotion is planned for spring 2021 before the hiking season begins. This will of course include Web-based promotion on CAI websites and social media channels.

2.4 Kinderleicht Wandern im Pongau

2.4.1 Background and brief description

GATE partner: Salzburg Research, in collaboration with SalzburgerLand Tourismus

Region/country: Pongau, Country of Salzburg , Austria

Pilot site: Pongau region, over 80 easy hikes for families with small children

Website: www.kinderleicht-wandern.net

Contact e-mail: guntram.geser@salzburgresearch.at

Brief description of the site:

Many hiking trails, farmed alp lodges and other attractions make the Salzburger Pongau a true hiking paradise for visitors of all ages and capabilities. Some of the villages of the Pongau are located in the Hohe Tauern National Park, and in most holiday regions mountain lifts allow reaching the starting point for many hikes. Kinderleicht Wandern im Salzburger Pongau is a new offer for families with small children that look for suitable trails. The Web application presents over 80 easy hikes of which 35 are stroller-friendly.

Number of visitors:

Pongau in the summer season May–October 2019: 866.348 guests staying overnight (all types of accommodation); overnight stays: 3.863.647 (average: 4.5); geographic origin of guests: domestic 27%, Germany 47%, other countries 26%.⁶

Application and content:

The Web application has been developed by Salzburg Research specifically for families with small children that look for suitable hiking trails. Some of the hikes could also be relevant for other GATE target groups. The website is based on WordPress and provides an online map of 82 easy hikes in the Pongau region of Salzburg, 35 of which useable with a stroller. Also some other attractions such as children's zoos and playgrounds are included. The information about the hikes comprises place of start/end, duration, length, difference in altitude, etc. and a downloadable map of the hike. Users need only a device (mobile, tablet, desktop) with a web-browser, no download of an app is necessary. Users can also rate hikes and share own information such as comments and images.

2.4.2 Development

Partner organisation

Kinderleicht Wandern im Pongau has been developed in cooperation with SalzburgerLand, the destination marketing organisation for the whole Country of Salzburg. One focus of SalzburgerLand in the summer season is of course hiking and they have a dedicated section "Kinderleicht.Wandern" on their website.⁷ The main themes of this section are hiking with the family, enjoying the nature and landscape, the farmed alp lodges (around 550 in the country) and the hospitality and culinary specialties they offer.

⁶ Land Salzburg: Tourismus - Sommersaison 2019, https://www.salzburg.gv.at/statistik/_Seiten/statistik-tourismus.aspx

⁷ SalzburgerLand: Kinderleicht.Wandern, <https://www.salzburgerland.com/de/kinderleicht-wandern/>

Pilot idea and content

One promotional product of SalzburgerLand is the “Kinderleicht Wandern” brochure that features easy hikes for families in the Pongau region. The brochure can be ordered freely from SalzburgerLand but is not made available for download as the high-resolution digital version has a quite large volume (about 100 Megabytes). Therefore, in a discussion with SalzburgerLand on a suitable GATE pilot, the idea came up to make the content of the brochure accessible with a Web application (18/02/2020).

The digital content was with ARGE Kartographie who produced the maps of the hiking trails. After an agreement of how to use the content (e.g. concerning copyrights), a package of 1.9 Gigabytes of map and image data was transferred to Salzburg Research (16/03/2020). The package included also the high-resolution digital version of the brochure, but not a separate file with the descriptions of the hiking trails and other attractions. Furthermore, the maps did not include the names of the hiking trails, the map scale (distance in meters) and the copyright of ARGE Kartographie. Therefore, we had to extract from the high-resolution PDF of the brochure the descriptions (text and details such as hike length, difference in altitude, etc.) and the maps which include the mentioned details. After the extraction, the content was prepared to allow easy filling of the database entry template for each hiking path or other attraction (preparation completed 07/05/2020).

Application development

As technical platform for the Kinderleicht Wandern application the open source WordPress software and for the map-based access to the information the Open Street Map are used. The development of the application required:

- Define the website concept and template for the information,
- Set up of the WordPress based Website and integrate Open Street Map,
- Fill for each hike and other attraction the template with the description and other details,
- Include for each hike the map, an image for other attractions,
- Tag each Point of Interest (100+) on Open Street Map,
- Test and improve the website, e.g. search functions, display of content, etc.

This work was completed on the 29th of June 2020. The sections that follow describe the content and functionality offered by the website.

Website content

Information about 82 easy hikes for families with small children in the Pongau region of Salzburg

35 of the hikes possible with a stroller

Also included are some other attractions such as children's zoos and playgrounds

The information about the hikes comprises

- Brief description
- Place of start/end
- Duration
- Length
- Difference in altitude
- Restaurants, incl. contact information

Ratings, comments and images shared by users

Kinderleicht Wandern

Filzmoos: Moosalm Kinderwanderweg

Talort: Filzmoos
Start: Parkplatz gegenüber der Tankstelle
Strecke: 2 km
Höhenmeter: 300
Dauer: 1 h 15 min

Vom Parkplatz geht es Richtung Kreisverkehr, dort nimmt man die erste Ausfahrt und biegt vor dem Hotel Alpenblick rechts ab. Es geht über eine Brücke, danach links bergauf durch den Wald. Auf dem Weg trifft man auf 15 kleine Häuschen – in jedem wohnt ein Tier. Sind alle 15 Tiere ins Heft gestempelt, ist das Ziel erreicht und man bekommt bei der Moosalm eine kleine Überraschung. Stempelhefte sind im Tourismusbüro erhältlich.

Seite drucken

Karte drucken

Karte speichern

Einkehrmöglichkeit:

Moosalm, T +43 (0) 664 5328002, ÖZ: Mai bis Okt

Bewertung - Erfahrungen - Fotos

Website functions

Based on WordPress,
incl. Open Street Map

Search functionalities

- Full text search
- Tags (keywords)
- Ratings with stars
- Result: list view with brief info and link to full information

Map-based search

- Tagged hikes
- Zoom into the map

User can download and print all information or only the map

Can also rate hikes and upload comments and own images (max. 10).

The screenshot displays the 'Kinderleicht Wandern' website interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Karte' and 'Liste' options. The main content area shows a list of hiking trails. The first trail is 'Bischofshofen: Wasserfallweg' with details: TALORT: Bischofshofen, START: Parkplatz Skisprungschanze, ZIEL: Gainfeldwasserfall, distance 3.8 km, elevation 239 hm, and time ca. 1h 30 min. Below this is 'Goldegg-Weng: Wanderung zur Hochleitnalm' with a map view showing the route and a pop-up window for more details. The right sidebar contains a search bar, a list of keywords, and a filter section.

2.4.3 Testing, launch and promotion

Testing

During the development of the website its functionality, display of content and other aspects were regularly tested and improved. On the 30th of June 2020 the website went online in a “soft launch” to allow selected organisations access, test and provide feedback on the website. This included the cooperation partner SalzburgerLand and the GATE partner independent L., who tested the website regarding the success criteria of the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG 2.1)⁸ and usability. Feedback from other organisations was received in response to the promotion activities (examples see below).

Promotion

The promotion goal for 2020 was to make the website known to relevant organisations in the region, including family/children hotels, tourism offices, and nature/hiking organisations.

For the promotion a flyer was designed that includes brief information about the content of the website, the website link (including as QR-code), the logos of the GATE project and regional partners, and the acknowledgment of the funding under the Interreg V-A Italia-Österreich programme, including

⁸ W3C (2018): Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1. W3C Recommendation, 5 June 2018, <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>

the European Union and Interreg programme logos. 5.000 flyers have been printed for distribution to/via hotels and tourism offices.

Individual e-mails were sent to 22 tourism offices, 31 medium-large size family/children hotels, and 10 contacts of regional groups of nature/hiking organisations (Alpenverein, Naturfreunde). The e-mails contained brief information about the website, the website link, the digital version of the flyer attached, and the request to make the website known to families with small children. The e-mailing to the tourism offices and hotels was followed by letters with the same content and a number of flyers (80-100 flyers) sent by postal services. This distribution was carried out from mid of July to begin of August (16/07-05/08/2020).

2.4.4 User feedback and data

Qualitative feedback

Hotels: In the e-mails from hotels, mainly concerning the flyers to be sent, responses referring to the website were very positive, for example:

- Hotel Gut Weissenhof (17/07/2020): „*Herzlichen Dank für Ihre E-Mail ... die Seite ist toll geworden ... Gerne können Sie uns Flyer zuschicken*“ (great website, send us flyers).
- Familienhotel - Ferienanlage Central (21/07/2020): „*Das ist ein sehr interessanter Link. Gerne geben wir Ihre Flyer an interessierte Gäste von uns weiter*“ (very interesting link, will hand out your flyers to interested guests).
- Filzmooserhof (16/07/2020): „*Sehr nette Idee euer ‚Kinderleicht Wandern in Pongau‘ und wird sicher gerne angenommen*“ (nice idea, people will like it).
- The latter respondent also informed us that a new family hike with playgrounds (“Bärtls Familienwanderweg”) has been created along an existing hiking path (included in Kinderleicht Wandern) but with a different start point. Therefore, the description on the website was changed and an available brochure for the new hiking path added.

Tourist offices: Some of the e-mails from tourist offices were helpful to improve the website content and keep it up-to-date:

- Tourismusverband Eben im Pongau (04/08/2020): Informed us that for one hiking path (KITIWAPF) the description of its two variants, one stroller-friendly the other not, was not fully clear. Therefore, the description on the website was changed and an available brochure added.
- Tourismusverband Filzmoos (04/09/2020): Requested changing the description of a hike („Wanderung zur Schwaigalm“) because the shuttle to the Schwaigalm was not available, perhaps due to the Corona pandemic.
- Altenmarkt-Zauchensee Tourismus (07/08/2020): Informed us that some positions of hiking paths in their area were not shown correctly in the map-view. It turned out that the tags were placed correctly but when published the OpenStreetMap moved them to the next “known” location. These tags had to be fixed with a special coding.

Quantitative results

The table and charts below show the accesses to the Kinderleicht Wandern website from August to October 2020. In this period the website had 524 interested visits in which in total 3.883 pages have been viewed (on average 7.4 pages per interested visit).

What are interested visits and page views: Firstly, there is a total number of visits (TV) by unique visitors (UV), who accessed the website one or more times. Interested visits are those in which more

than only the first page (OFP) was accessed. OFP visits are subtracted from both the total of visits and the total of page views. The remaining figures are the interested visits and page views. These figures include only few accesses of web pages by the website manager. Changes of the content of pages (as described above) are carried out internal to the system, but the manager also checks if these are displayed correctly. When these accesses are subtracted the total number of interested visits is still slightly over 500.

Month	Unique visitors (UV)	Total visits (TV)	Total page views (TPV)	Only first page (OFP)	Interested visits (TV minus OFP)	Interested page views (TPV minus OFP)	Interested page views/visit on average
2020-08	328	443	1.906	203	240	1.703	7.1
2020-09	265	350	1.375	197	153	1.178	7.7
2020-10	244	310	1.181	179	131	1.002	7.6
	837	1.103	4.462	579	524	3.883	7.4

Of the around 500 interested visits of the Kinderleicht Wandern website in the period August to October 2020 most, perhaps over 400, were very likely by guests in the Pongau region. In the period

there were 310 downloads of maps of 63 hiking trails, including maps that present more than one trail. The functions to rate, comment on and upload images of hiking trails and other attractions have not been used in the period. In the future, this will require special promotion.

2.4.5 Plans for next steps

The Kinderleicht Wandern im Pongau website will be kept running in its current form in 2021, and minor changes and additions of the content requested for example by tourism offices will be included.

As Salzburg Research is a centre for technological research and development it cannot oblige to service developed solutions on a regular basis. Therefore, the intention is to hand over the website to SalzburgerLand Tourism or an organisation commissioned by them to maintain it.

The application allows easy extension of the information by adding new hiking trails and more detailed trail description and media (e.g. brochures, images, videos).

The website includes also functionality for users to rate, comment on and upload own images of trails and other attractions. With strong promotion this could be used to enrich the website and enhance the appeal of the hiking region Pongau for families with small children.

3 Lessons learned

This chapter summarises important lessons learned by the GATE pilot sites in the realisation of their new IT applications. The pilot sites developed applications of information technologies for different kinds of tourism offers, including the Bletterbach area and gorge (part of the World Heritage Dolomites), the nature park Parco Rossi, the Sentiero della Sensibilità of CAI Alpago, and the offer of hiking trails for families with small children in the Pongau region in the Country of Salzburg.

The main lessons learned relate to the topics of collaboration in multidisciplinary teams, narration and content, flexibility of IT applications, participation of users in the development, and of course the impact of the COVID-19 crisis.

Collaboration

Projects aimed to make nature experiences accessible to all require the collaboration of a team with multi-disciplinary expertise.

independent L., who coordinated the development of the Bletterbach Gorge Virtual Reality Experience, observed, *“that the exchange of experience and the integration of subject-specific skills in a wide range of areas is of crucial importance for the success of the product and the subsequent user experience”*.

The Parco Rossi project team emphasised, *“To develop a complex project of innovation, the winning strategy is the ability to work in a multidisciplinary team, where processes of knowledge sharing, collaboration and problem solving are activated. To realize an accessibility project you need to know how to be inclusive”*.

In the development of the Sentiero della Sensibilità of CAI Alpago also had to collaborate closely with public and private entities. The 24 km long route crosses through the areas of three municipalities and seven Regole, which are collective properties belonging to local families. This required agreements and cooperation with and among these entities based on a common understanding and willingness to support in making the trail barrier-free as well as the installation of iBeacons.

In GATE, the opportunity the pilot sites had to discuss pilot ideas, the development and specific issues with other partners of the cross-border project also often helped to implement solutions according to best practice.

Required expertise

The expertise necessary for a successful IT application includes project management, user-centered design, content creation and integration, technical development, and ensuring access to and usability of the application for everyone.

Excellent project management enables all team members to play to their strengths, and together drive the project forward, against all odds (even the Coronavirus crisis). User-centered design requires involving end-users, particularly people with disabilities, early on in the project and up until the final testing and launch of the application.

The required specific expertise regarding content, technology, access and usability depends on the type of IT application to be developed. While some IT solutions are relatively easy to implement (e.g., a standard Web app or WordPress-based website), for others highly specialised skills regarding both content and technology are required.

Narration and content

Not every IT application has a narrative dimension, e.g. the main purpose of the Kinderleicht Wandern website is to provide information about the existence of easy hikes for families with small children. If the application is narrative, dedicated work is necessary for the storyboard, interaction design, and creation of the multimedia content, which may include texts, speech and sound recordings, images, videos, graphic animations, and even historical re-enactments as in Parco Rossi's INgame.

In the case of CAI Alpago's Web App Sentiero della Sensibilità, rich content for 14 points of interest (with iBeacons) has been created, and the musical path with parts of Richard Strauss' Alpine Symphony plays a great role in emotionally binding together the stories about the cultural landscape.

The more specialised the technology is, the more effort is necessary to create and particularly integrate the content for telling the story. This is the case with the Virtual Reality (VR) experience of the Bletterbach Gorge and the Augmented Reality (AR) in the INgame chatbot of Parco Rossi. It also applies to the fine-tuned integration of physical elements (e.g. panel, relief, Braille), Capacitive touch sensors and recorded stories of the Villa Rossi 3D model.

Work by specialised providers was necessary for the VR, AR, 3D printing and touch sensor solutions, of course. The high standards of such providers regarding professionalism, technology and content greatly add to the successful realisation of a project.

Flexible applications

In the end, what counts most regarding the IT application, be it VR or AR, a chatbot, a multimedia guide or a WordPress-based website, is that it be as easy as possible to access and use by everyone. However, the application must also work for the operator as regards costs of maintenance and updates, for instance. In this regard, it is worth noting that the flexibility of a Web app makes it easy to keep information up-to-date and add new content, such as adding points of interest (with Beacons or QR-codes) on the Sentiero della Sensibilità or, thanks to the Web-CMS WordPress, new easy hikes to the Kinderleicht Wandern, for example.

More important for the inclusiveness of an IT application is choice regarding modes of use. The Sentiero della Sensibilità app and Parco Rossi's INgame have text and image or audio for visually impaired people as basic modes. Videos in INgame have a dramaturgy and a voice-over that supports this group of users. Historical re-enactment videos with speech come with Italian sign language or subtitles in the English version for users with a hearing impairment.

Participation of users

As mentioned above, people with disabilities should be involved in the development early on in the project and up until the final testing and launch of the IT application. However, the client and operator of the solution must be involved too, as they also have to support the goals of the heritage or tourism organisation.

The pilot sites used various methods to ensure that the final products would meet the requirements of the end-users as well as of the organisations. These include, among others: Workshops of the developers with staff of visitor centres, museum curators, and experts for digital accessibility. Meetings with people with disabilities to present the project and collect user needs and suggestions. Following the principles of Design for All and user-centered design, e.g. involving people with disabilities as consultants in the design phase. Testing of the functionality, Web Content Accessibility Guidelines compliance and usability of the IT application. Presentation of the beta version and collection of feedback at public events. Online feedback by tourist offices and hotels. Final testing in the field, e.g.

in the park or on the hiking trail, including technical aspects (e.g. Internet connection, GPS location, interactivity of iBeacons), and interviews on user satisfaction.

The pilot sites received many helpful suggestions for the design and improvement of the developed IT applications. Regarding the involvement of the end-users in development, the CAI Alpage group notes, *“The opinion of end-users is more important in the development phase than in the test phase. In fact, if the involvement of end-users takes place only in the testing of the application, it will not be possible to change the general functioning of the tool, but only to modify the existing one.”*

Impact of the COVID-19 crisis

The health protection measures against the Coronavirus obviously had a strong impact on the pilot sites. Some of the work was completed already in 2019, but starting from March 2020 the development of the IT applications at times was disrupted, particularly where face-to-face and on-site work was necessary. The Kinderleicht Wandern, which did not require on-site work, went online in July 2020, but the other pilots could not roll out their applications in the summer season. Meanwhile all are tested, completed and available for the next season, and there are plans on how to proceed.

However, the impact of the COVID-19 crisis goes much deeper. On the one hand, there is an increased demand for being in natural environments, hiking and visiting nature parks, and it must be ensured that people with disabilities are not left behind. Organisations with a mandate and expertise for this should now boost their efforts, and may actually benefit from the heightened interest in nature tourism.

On the other hand, all operators of tourist facilities must come to terms with the requirements of health protection and the sensitivity of visitors regarding contact with other people and things. The need to keep a certain distance from others will require limiting the number of visitors at peak times as well as managing their flow through reception and exhibition spaces.

Moreover, the IT installations for visitors with controls to be touched, e.g. keyboards, touchscreens, headsets and others, will be affected. With the COVID-19 crisis, such installations have been closed down, and in the future many visitors will remain sensitive and not use them. Therefore, in the coming years touchless controls based on voice and gesture recognition will be an important topic concerning IT installations for the communication of cultural and natural heritage.